

STORAGE RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE ECO-SYSTEM

4th TNA Call Documentation – User

USER REPORT (WITH SATISFACTION SURVEY): USER (S)

General information about the project	
Project title (as used in application)	Effective Energy Management in ORC, BESS and TES integrated systems
Project acronym (max 15 characters)	EEMOBTIS
StoRIES TNA RI(s) accessed	Birmingham Centre for Energy Storage
Keywords (up to ten, free text)	Organic Rankine Cycle, Thermal Energy Storage, Battery Energy Storage Systems, Energy Optimization
Arrival date (in town where RI located)	25/06/2024
Departure date (from town where RI located)	30/08/2024
Starting date of access (first day at RI)	26/06/2024
Finishing date of access (last day at RI)	29/08/2024
Number of days not using the RI (during the above period)	N/A
Reason for not using RI those days (describe)	N/A
Number of days using the RI	Used throughout the whole stay
Number of users granted access (group size)	1
Comments	RI involved cluster computer which was continuously used to generate project outputs.
Access Summary Report - work performed and initial results	
Brief description of the objectives of your project (up to 200 words)	
<p>This project explores a hybrid energy storage system (HESS) configuration for industrial waste heat recovery. The system integrates a Latent Heat Thermal Energy Storage Unit (LHTES) and an Organic Rankine Cycle (ORC) for the conversion of waste heat to electricity, and a Battery Energy Storage System (BESS) for providing and storing direct electricity. The ORC serves as the primary energy conversion unit, transforming thermal energy from waste heat to electrical power. The TES unit is incorporated to store excess heat, so that it can provide sufficient power to the ORC to meet demand when there is low waste heat availability, ensuring a consistent supply to the ORC even when waste heat availability fluctuates. The BESS is used to store electrical power when the cost of electricity is low (during off peak hours) and to assist in demand response with a much faster energy</p>	

discharge rate than the TES-ORC process, allowing the TES unit to store energy to be used when BESS is charging, minimizing the total electricity that needs to be bought from the market. Therefore, the main objective of this project is to identify the contribution of each component in the HESS configuration (Figure 1) to offer superior performance.

Figure 1 : Hybrid Energy Storage Configuration for Industrial Waste Heat Recovery

Activities performed (up to 600 words)

The first objective of this work is the effective modelling of each process (TES, ORC, BESS). The goal is to use models that provide the essential information about the systems, such as State of Charge, Heat to Power output, and strike a good balance between model complexity and reliability. We need to have models that can be used for rapid assessment of the configuration without sacrificing predictive accuracy.

For modelling the battery energy storage system (BESS), the first order equivalent circuit model (ECM) was selected. This model consists of a voltage source, a resistor, and a capacitor. The voltage source represents the open-circuit voltage (OCV) of the battery, which varies with the State of Charge (SoC). The series resistance models the internal resistance of the battery, capturing the voltage drop during charging and discharging. A parallel combination of a resistor and a capacitor represents the transient response of the battery, modelling the short-term and long-term dynamic behaviour [1]. The first order ECM model was chosen due to its computational efficiency, crucial for real-time applications where rapid decision-making is essential [2]. Additionally, it offers adequate accuracy for the specific application, effectively capturing essential battery dynamics without the complexity of higher-order models. Euler's method was used to solve the ordinary differential equations (ODEs) associated with the model. This straightforward numerical procedure is suitable for real-time applications with limited computational resources. The State of Charge (SoC) was calculated at each timestep using Euler's method, providing a crucial parameter for monitoring BESS performance within the hybrid energy storage system.

Empirical correlations are chosen for modelling the Organic Rankine Cycle (ORC) due to their extensive experimental validation, reflecting real-world operating conditions derived from over 200 studies, ensuring reliability for practical applications [3]. They offer a straightforward and computationally efficient approach, reducing the complexity and computational burden associated with finite volume simulations, thus enabling faster analysis and decision-making. Additionally, these correlations have demonstrated accuracy and robustness across a range of experimental setups and conditions, providing confidence in their predictive capabilities. Finally, the practical relevance of these correlations ensures they account for real-world variables, making them highly applicable for system design and optimization.

For the development of the Latent Heat Thermal Energy Storage (LHTES) Unit, a one-dimensional dynamic model is used, focusing on the heat transfer between the waste heat stream and the phase change material (PCM) [4]. This model simplifies the complex thermal dynamics into a set of ordinary differential equations representing the energy conservation within discrete control volumes along the length of the storage unit. The model incorporates the thermophysical properties of the waste heat and the PCM, accounting for temperature-dependent specific heat curves and phase transitions. Heat transfer is described using radial conduction and forced convection, with the overall heat transfer coefficient dynamically calculated. The governing equations include the rate of change of internal energy for both waste heat and PCM. This model exhibits a root mean square error of <math><0.53\text{ }^\circ\text{C}</math> when validated against experimental data, ensuring computational efficiency and accuracy.

After setting up these models for each process, the goal was to work on a case study that focuses on the implementation of a hybrid energy storage system tailored for the recovery of industrial waste heat. The primary objective of this system is to capture and store waste heat generated from industrial processes, thereby enhancing energy efficiency and minimizing thermal waste. The accompanying graph illustrates the daily variations in the waste heat stream's mass flow rate and temperature over a 24-hour period.

References

[1] Yang, Yuqing, et al. "Modelling and optimal energy management for battery energy storage systems in renewable energy systems: A review." *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 167 (2022): 112671. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2022.112671>

[2] Rosewater, David M., et al. "Battery energy storage models for optimal control." *IEEE access* 7 (2019): 178357-178391. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2957698>

[3] Park, Byung-Sik, et al. "Review of Organic Rankine Cycle experimental data trends." *Energy conversion and management* 173 (2018): 679-691. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2018.07.097>

[4] Bastida, Hector, Ivan De la Cruz-Loredo, and Carlos E. Ugalde-Loo. "Effective one-dimensional dynamic modelling of latent heat thermal energy storage units for heating applications." *IET Energy Systems Integration* (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1049/esi2.12128>

Scientific results (up to 800 words)

Having these models at our disposal, we present a case study in a typical industrial setting. In this study, we examine the HESS in a typical industrial setting (adjusted from [5]) with, where the waste heat stream can be shown in the following Figure 2:

Figure 2 : Waste Heat Stream variation during the day (adjusted from [5]).

At the start of the day, both the mass flow rate and temperature of the waste heat are relatively low, and during the morning we see a rise in both parameters, corresponding to the startup phase of the industrial process. During the afternoon, both the mass flow rate and the temperature reach their peaks, as this period represents the peak operational hours of the industry, where the equipment is working at full capacity, leading to maximum waste heat generation. During the evening, a steady decline in both parameters indicates a slowdown in industrial activities. As processes slow down, the generation of waste heat reduces. The low and stable levels during the night suggest minimal industrial activities. This period corresponds to maintenance periods when most equipment is running at a minimal capacity to ensure stable operation.

The electricity demand fluctuations during the day are presented in Figure 3. Examining the pattern of this profile, we can see that when the facility begins operations in the morning, there is a gradual increase in power usage from 10kW to 30kW, as equipment starts working. During peak production, energy intensive processes drive the power demand up to the maximum of 70kW. In the evening hours, as production slows down, power demand decreases from 70kW to 40kW as equipment is gradually slowing down. During nighttime, minimal operations take place, with only essential equipment running, reducing demand back to 10kW.

Figure 3 : Daily Electrical Power Demand and Electricity prices (from [6])

Both waste heat stream and electrical power demand profiles follow diurnal variations, matching industrial operation cycles.

We implement a rule-based strategy to simulate this case study and figure out the way the power of each component is going to be supplied to the system.

The Waste Heat Stream can be split to either feed the ORC directly or go through the TES unit to store energy. The TES unit exhibits two charging/discharging cycles. The TES charges in the early morning hours when there is lower electricity demand, that the ORC mostly and then the BESS can cover. This stored energy is discharged between 12:00 and 14:00 to complement ORC and BESS, where there is high electricity demand and medium waste heat availability, as processes are still ramping up. This period is critical because it is the only time during the day when both TES and BESS discharge energy. This is because the waste heat stream itself cannot provide enough power output. The second charge cycle occurs during peak production hours when there is high waste heat availability, and it is noted that since the waste heat stream's temperature is higher during these hours, the charging time is significantly less. The second discharge cycle occurs

during the nighttime, when there is low waste heat availability, and the BESS needs to charge, as electricity prices are lower during the night. The charging cycles can be visualized by showing the percentage of Waste Heat to ORC and TES in Figure 4.

Figure 4 : Distribution of Waste Heat to TES and ORC

The heat stream that is discharged from the TES provides input to the ORC, and specifically for the TES-ORC conversion, the output power to the electrical demand, as described above, is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5 : TES-ORC power output

The main component for covering the electrical demand, is the ORC, which is the component that converts waste heat directly to electricity. With the input mass flow rate and temperature of the waste heat stream that is not diverted to the TES we calculate the daily power output. The ORC output power is shown in Figure 6. This plot aligns with the prior expectations of this component's performance as it exhibits a diurnal pattern as well, providing maximum power when there is the maximum waste heat availability, showing a consistent operation.

Figure 6 : Standalone ORC Output Power

As for the BESS, we expect to see that it charges overnight when electricity prices are lower, and discharge power during the day, ultimately saving on energy that needs to be bought during medium and high peak hours, reducing the total cost, and allowing the TES unit to store energy that is going to be used when the BESS is charging overnight. The power of the BESS is shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7 : Energy Charged and Discharged from BESS (left), and BESS power output to the electricity demand (right)

The SoC for the Energy Storage components, as described, is shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8 : Energy Storage Components' SoC

The entire system's performance, with the integration of all the components is shown in Figure 9. This Figure shows the whole HESS's power output to the demand, against the electricity demand profile, showing how much electricity demand can be covered via the HESS schematic, and how much electricity needs to be bought from the market directly.

Figure 9 : HESS Power output against the electrical demand

References

[5] Le Roux, D., Touzo, A., Esence, T., & Olivès, R. (2022). Experimental and numerical investigation of the temperature and flow rate variation on an industrial high-temperature thermocline storage for recovering waste heat. *Journal of Energy Storage*, 55, 105656. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.est.2022.105656>

[6] <https://www.sms-plc.com/insights/smarter-energy-consumption-on-the-rise-with-introduction-of-time-of-use-tariffs/>

Interpretation of the results (up to 400 words)

Examining the results of each component individually, the following conclusions can be drawn:

Thermal Energy Storage Unit results:

1. The morning charging cycle is longer as the waste heat stream's temperature is lower, when comparing to the midday charging cycle which is approx. 4 times faster, as the waste heat stream's temperature is much higher.
2. TES is discharged during 12:00 and 15:00 to aid in demand response, as the mass flow rate of the waste heat stream has not reached its peak, but there is higher electricity demand than the morning.
3. TES is discharged overnight to allow the BESS to charge at a cheaper rate, supplementing the lower waste heat availability that is fed directly to the ORC. This leads to cheap charge of BESS and ultimately lower cost from buying electricity directly from the market, leading to an overall better performing system in terms of costs.

Organic Rankine Cycle results:

1. The power provided by the ORC follows diurnal variations, matching industrial operational cycles, showing consistent energy conversion.
2. Consistent day-night output reflects regular waste heat production in continuous industrial processes, aligning well with typical industrial shift changes.
3. Results show low but steady waste heat conversion due to maintenance, efficiency and continuous operations, as many industrial processes operate continuously or with minimal downtime to maintain efficiency and production schedules.

Battery Energy Storage System's results:

1. The BESS performs as expected, charging overnight and discharging during the day. It is notable that the discharge rate is higher during high peak hours than the discharge rate during morning hours, showcasing the ability of the BESS to match demand patterns in a rapid fashion, which was the major advantage of this hybrid energy storage configuration.
2. BESS discharges energy all throughout the day at different rates, to allow the charging of the TES unit, so that it can be used when the BESS is not going to be available (which is the time when the BESS is charging), to ensure that there is always energy available to be used to cover part of the demand.

Overall, this thermal-electrical hybrid energy storage system configuration shows promise in recovering waste heat in industrial settings, by utilising the advantages of each subcomponent and process to handle energy flows.

Main achievements during the TNA related work (up to 250 words)

The primary achievements of this work revolve around the development and implementation of a hybrid energy storage system for industrial waste heat recovery, leveraging Thermal Energy Storage, Organic Rankine Cycle and Battery Energy Storage System integration. Key accomplishments include:

1. **Integrated System Model Development:** A comprehensive model integrating ORC, TES and BESS was developed. This model effectively simulates the conversion of waste heat into electricity and the subsequent storage and utilization of this energy.
2. **Simulation and Optimization:** Extensive simulations were conducted to assess the performance of the integrated system under various operational scenarios. These simulations demonstrated significant improvements in energy conversion efficiency and system reliability, particularly under fluctuating waste heat conditions.
3. **Case study implementation:** A detailed case study was conducted, applying the developed model to a realistic simulated industrial setup. The results highlighted the system's ability to enhance waste heat recovery, meet electricity demands, and reduce dependency on external power sources.
4. **Scalability and Adaptability:** The models developed in this project have been designed for scalability, allowing their application across different industrial contexts. The adaptability of the ORC-TES-BESS configuration ensures that it can be tailored to varying waste heat availability and energy demands.
5. **Framework for broader applications:** The successful development and testing of the integrated system model provide a framework for broader applications in sustainable energy management. This framework can be utilized for further research and development, contributing advancements in energy efficiency and environmental sustainability.

Difficulties during the TNA related work (up to 250 words)

There were complications related to attaining access to cluster computer due to short time frame of visit. These were overcome with collaboration between team members. Furthermore, there was a higher accuracy ORC model available by host, but there were unforeseen complexities that did not allow us to properly integrate it with the TES and BESS model in the given timeframe of the STORIES project. Close collaboration between the two parties in ongoing to achieve this and will be reflected in a peer-reviewed journal publication.

Intended publications

“Assessment of a Thermal-Electrical Hybrid Energy Storage system configuration for Industrial Waste Heat Recovery” - 28th Conference on Process Integration, Modelling and Optimization for Energy Saving and Pollution Reduction (PRES'25), Port Dickson, Malaysia
[\(https://www.pres2025.com/\)](https://www.pres2025.com/)

“An effective predictor of packed bed latent heat storage fluid dynamics using Artificial Intelligence models” – Energy Journals

Data management

The models and data obtained from this work are to be used in joint dissemination activities, acknowledging the StoRIES project contribution.

Conclusions / additional comments					
<p>During our collaboration with the RI, from daily discussions, another piece of work was proposed that is about effectively predicting the dynamic operation of packed bed latent heat storage systems using Artificial Intelligence models. This is also output of this project as this idea would not be real without the daily interaction with the team from the University of Birmingham and the visiting researcher. StoRIES will be acknowledged in that research paper as well.</p> <p>I would like to express my sincere gratitude to the European Commission and the StoRIES project for providing me with the opportunity to conduct research at the Birmingham Centre for Energy Storage. This invaluable experience at a world-leading laboratory has greatly contributed to the advancement of my knowledge in thermal energy storage technologies.</p>					
<p>Did you complete the EC user questionnaire available at https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/RIsurveyUSERS ? (necessary) Contribution ID: 82bf4c16-c429-495d-a20e-d0115361dcfe</p>					
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No					
Feedback – HSE, Ethics and Satisfaction					
Please rate on a scale from 1 (excellent) to 5 (poor). Feel free to provide additional comments					
Practical information on how to apply for Transnational Access and the overall application process	1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
[Comment]					
Information provided, once your project was accepted, on how to proceed	1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
[Comment]					
Support received at the site(s) regarding technical/scientific matters and logistics	Have you got sufficient support from the RI staff during the project? If not, please, specify the problems. <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No				
[Please specify any problems]					
RI extension / upgrades required	In your opinion, is the RI needed to be upgraded? If yes, please give an explanation. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				

<i>[Please specify]</i>	
Problems with local regulations	Have you had any problems with regulations of the visited RI owner (HSE, lab working hours, etc.)? If yes, please, specify <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
<i>[Please specify]</i>	
Health and safety issues	Did you encounter any health or safety issue during your research? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
<i>[Please provide details]</i>	
Environment & Ethics	Did your research involve the use of elements that may cause harm to the environment, to animals or plants? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
<i>[Please provide details]</i>	
Environment & Ethics	Did your research deal with endangered fauna and/or flora and/or protected areas? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
<i>[Please provide details]</i>	
Environment & Ethics	Did your research involve the use of elements that may cause harm to humans, including research staff? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
<i>[Please provide details]</i>	
Environment & Ethics – Dual use	Does your research have the potential for military applications? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
<i>[Please provide details]</i>	
Environment & Ethics – Misuse	Does your research have the potential for malevolent /criminal/terrorist abuse? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
<i>[Please provide details]</i>	

Environmental issues	Were any potentially dangerous substances (materials / gases etc.) released into the environment (atmosphere, water, or land)? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
<i>[Please provide details]</i>					
Ethics issues	Are there any other ethics issues that should be taken into consideration? Please specify <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
<i>[Please provide details]</i>					
Overall impression of communication and interaction after finishing your TNA related work	1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<i>[Comment]</i>					
Suggestions for facilities not included in StoRIES which you would use for your research					
Suggestions how StoRIES can improve future TNA programme, how to make the TNA more impactful on the energy storage technologies and how to enable the achievement of high TRL levels.					
Feedback – Pro-active Innovation Support					
Awareness	Did you know about the pro-active innovation support of StoRIES. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
Personal experience					
Personal experience	Have you taken advantage of or benefited from the pro-active innovation support? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
Information/service provided by the pro-active innovation support?	1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)

	<input type="checkbox"/>				

I declare that the above provided information and especially that information on the number of days visited the RI is correct.

